

A NOTE ON SMALL SOLUTIONS TO DIAGONAL CONGRUENCES

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Abstract

Using a result of Chow, Lindqvist, and Prendiville, we establish that for any positive integer k , positive integer n with $n \geq \frac{3}{2}k(\log k + \log \log k + 2 + O(\log \log k / \log k))$, prime p , integer c , and integers a_i , with $p \nmid a_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, there exists a solution to $a_1x_1^k + a_2x_2^k + \cdots + a_nx_n^k \equiv c \pmod{p}$ with $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

1. Introduction

For prime p and positive integer k , let $\Gamma(k, p)$ denote the minimal positive integer n such that for any integers a_i with $p \nmid a_i$, $1 \leq i \leq n$, and integer c ,

$$a_1x_1^k + a_2x_2^k + \cdots + a_nx_n^k \equiv c \pmod{p} \quad (1)$$

has a solution. In [5], Cochrane, Ostergaard, and Spencer were able to obtain solutions to Equation (1) with $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ when $n \geq \frac{3}{2}(k^2 + k + 2)$. The goal of this paper is to lower the required number of variables needed to obtain solutions to Equation (1) with variables of size $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Of note,

by looking at the congruence $\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^k \equiv \frac{p-1}{2} \pmod{p}$, we see that $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ is optimal.

Obtaining small solutions has been studied for homogeneous congruences as well. For homogeneous congruences of the form

$$a_1x_1^k + a_2x_2^k + \cdots + a_nx_n^k \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \tag{2}$$

where the a_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, are integers and p is prime, Schmidt [10] found that when k is odd, $\epsilon > 0$, and n is sufficiently large, Equation (2) has a solution with $\max_i |x_i| \leq p^\epsilon$. Later, Schmidt [11] showed that for $a_i \in \mathbb{Z}$, $1 \leq i \leq n$, p a prime, odd $k \geq 3$, $\epsilon > 0$, and a constant $c(k)$ depending only on k , Equation (2) has a solution with

$$\max_i |x_i| \ll_{n,\epsilon} p^{\frac{1}{3} + \sqrt{\frac{c(k)}{n}} + \epsilon}.$$

Baker [1] found that for a natural number m , $\epsilon > 0$, and integers a_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, a non-zero solution to the congruence

$$a_1x_1^k + a_2x_2^k + \cdots + a_nx_n^k \equiv 0 \pmod{m} \tag{3}$$

can be found when

$$\max_i |x_i| < \begin{cases} m^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2(n-1)} + \epsilon}, & \text{for } n \geq 4; \\ m^{\frac{2}{3} + \epsilon}, & \text{for } n = 3. \end{cases}$$

In the case of $k = 3$, Dietmann [7] showed that Equation (3) has a solution when

$$\max_i |x_i| \leq \begin{cases} m^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2n}}, & \text{for } n \text{ odd}; \\ m^{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2(n-1)}}, & \text{for } n \text{ even}. \end{cases}$$

In [2, Lemma 10.1], Baker further refined his bound on solutions to homogeneous congruences with a composite modulus by proving that for a natural number m , $\epsilon > 0$, integers a_i , $1 \leq i \leq n$, and $n \geq C(k, \epsilon)$ where $C(k, \epsilon)$ is a constant, Equation (3) has a solution with

$$\max_i |x_i| \leq m^{\frac{1}{k} + \epsilon}.$$

This paper uses smooth numbers and a result from the work of Chow, Lindqvist and Prendiville [4] to lower the number of variables needed to establish a solution for Equation (1) with $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Using this result we are able to reduce the number of variables needed from $n \geq \frac{3}{2}(k^2 + k + 2)$ to

$$n \geq \frac{3}{2}k(\log k + \log \log k + 2 + O(\log \log k / \log k)).$$

Theorem 1. *For any positive integer k , positive integer n with*

$$n \geq \begin{cases} 9, & \text{for } k = 2; \\ 12, & \text{for } k = 3; \\ \frac{3}{2}k(\log k + \log \log k + 2 + O(\log \log k / \log k)), & \text{for } k \geq 4; \end{cases}$$

prime p , integer c , and integers a_i , with $p \nmid a_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$, there exists a solution to Equation (1) with $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

2. Preliminary Results

First, we introduce the new result that leads to the reduction in the size of n . For any positive real number η and positive integer B , we define $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}(B, B^\eta)$ to be the set

$$\mathcal{A} := \{x \in [1, B] \cap \mathbb{Z} : p \text{ prime, } p \mid x \text{ implies } p \leq B^\eta\},$$

which we call the set of B^η -smooth numbers. Now we are able to state the following theorem, shown by Chow, Lindqvist, and Prendiville [4].

Theorem 2 ([4], Theorem B.1). *Let $c_1, \dots, c_s \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ with $\sum_{i \in I} c_i = 0$ for some non-empty subset I of $\{1, 2, \dots, s\}$. Then, for $k \geq 2$, there exists a positive real number $\eta_0(k)$ and positive integers $s_0(k)$ and $N_0(\underline{c}, \eta, k)$ such that for $0 < \eta \leq \eta_0(k)$, $s \geq s_0(k)$ and $N \geq N_0(\underline{c}, \eta, k)$, we have*

$$\#\left\{ \underline{x} \in \mathcal{A}(N, N^\eta)^s : \sum_{i=1}^s c_i x_i^k = 0 \right\} \asymp_{\underline{c}, \eta, k} N^{s-k}.$$

Moreover, one can take $s_0(2) = 5$, $s_0(3) = 8$, and for $k \geq 4$,

$$s_0(k) = k(\log k + \log \log k + 2 + O(\log \log k / \log k)).$$

Let

$$N_{\mathcal{A}^n} := \#\left\{ (\underline{x}, \underline{y}) \in \mathcal{A}^n \times \mathcal{A}^n : \sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_i^k \equiv \sum_{i=1}^n a_i y_i^k \pmod{p} \right\},$$

$$\tilde{N}_{\mathcal{A}^n} := \#\left\{ (\underline{x}, \underline{y}) \in \mathcal{A}^n \times \mathcal{A}^n : \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^k \equiv \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^k \pmod{p} \right\},$$

and

$$S_{\mathcal{A}^n} := \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_i^k \in \mathbb{Z}_p : \underline{x} \in \mathcal{A}^n \right\}.$$

We define the *Dickman function*, $\rho(u)$, which is the continuous function on the non-negative real numbers that is uniquely defined by the differential equation $u\rho'(u) = -\rho(u - 1)$, with the initial condition that $\rho(u) = 1$ for $u \in [0, 1]$.

In the following lemma we will consider the set of B^η -smooth numbers, and we will use the bound

$$|\mathcal{A}| = |\mathcal{A}(B, B^\eta)| = B\rho\left(\frac{1}{\eta}\right) + O\left(\frac{B}{\log B}\right),$$

which was established by Ramaswami [8].

Let $\eta_0(k)$ and $s_0(k)$ be defined as in Theorem 2. We also define the additive character $e_p(\cdot) = e^{2\pi i(\cdot)/p}$. We can now prove the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *For any positive integers k and n and prime p with $k \geq 2$, $0 < \eta \leq \eta_0(k)$, $2n \geq s_0(k)$, $nB^k \leq p$, and integers a_i with $(a_i, p) = 1$, $1 \leq i \leq n$, we have $|S_{\mathcal{A}^n}| \gg_{k,n,\eta} B^k$.*

Proof. The statement is trivial if B is less than a constant depending only on η and k , so we may assume that B is sufficiently large in terms of η and k , as needed. Using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{A}|^{2n} &= \left(\sum_{z \in S_{\mathcal{A}^n}} \# \left\{ \underline{x} \in \mathcal{A}^n : \sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_i^k \equiv z \pmod{p} \right\} \right)^2 \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{z \in S_{\mathcal{A}^n}} 1 \right) \sum_{z \in S_{\mathcal{A}^n}} \left(\# \left\{ \underline{x} \in \mathcal{A}^n : \sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_i^k \equiv z \pmod{p} \right\} \right)^2 \\ &= |S_{\mathcal{A}^n}| N_{\mathcal{A}^n}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have that $|S_{\mathcal{A}^n}| \geq |\mathcal{A}|^{2n}/N_{\mathcal{A}^n}$.

Now we consider $N_{\mathcal{A}^n}$. Note that, by Hölder's inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} N_{\mathcal{A}^n} &= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{\lambda=1}^p \sum_{\underline{x}, \underline{y} \in \mathcal{A}^n} e_p \left(\lambda \left(\sum_{i=1}^n a_i x_i^k - \sum_{i=1}^n a_i y_i^k \right) \right) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{p} \sum_{\lambda=1}^p \prod_{i=1}^n \left| \sum_{x_i \in \mathcal{A}} e_p(\lambda a_i x_i^k) \right|^2 \\ &\leq \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{p} \sum_{\lambda=1}^p \left| \sum_{x \in \mathcal{A}} e_p(\lambda a_i x^k) \right|^{2n} \right)^{1/n}. \end{aligned}$$

We notice that

$$\frac{1}{p} \sum_{\lambda=1}^p \left| \sum_{x \in \mathcal{A}} e_p(\lambda a_i x^k) \right|^{2n}$$

counts the number of solutions to the congruence

$$a_i(x_1^k + \cdots + x_n^k) \equiv a_i(y_1^k + \cdots + y_n^k) \pmod{p}.$$

Since $(a_i, p) = 1$, this is the number of solutions to

$$x_1^k + \cdots + x_n^k \equiv y_1^k + \cdots + y_n^k \pmod{p}. \tag{4}$$

In conclusion, $N_{\mathcal{A}^n} \leq \tilde{N}_{\mathcal{A}^n}$. Since $nB^k \leq p$, any solution to Equation (4) with $1 \leq x_i, y_i \leq B$ is a solution to $x_1^k + \cdots + x_n^k = y_1^k + \cdots + y_n^k$. Thus, we have by Theorem 2 that $\tilde{N}_{\mathcal{A}^n} \ll_{k,n,\eta} B^{2n-k}$, so $N_{\mathcal{A}^n} \ll_{k,n,\eta} B^{2n-k}$. For B sufficiently large, we have that $|\mathcal{A}| > \frac{1}{2}\rho\left(\frac{1}{\eta}\right)B$. Therefore, we find that $|\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{A}^n}| \gg_{k,n,\eta} B^k$. \square

We now recall two lemmas from [5]. The first lemma follows from the Cauchy-Davenport Theorem [3, 6].

Lemma 2 ([5], Lemma 8.1). *For any prime p and positive integer k , we have $\Gamma(k, p) \leq k$.*

We define the following *sumset* and *product set* notation. For $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_p$, we use $A + B = \{a + b : a \in A, b \in B\}$ and $AB = \{ab : a \in A, b \in B\}$.

The following lemma is a direct consequence of a result of Sárközy [9, Corollary A].

Lemma 3 ([5], Lemma 8.3). *If A_1, A_2, A_3 , and D are subsets of \mathbb{Z}_p with $|A_1||A_2||A_3||D| > p^3$, then $A_1D + A_2 + A_3 = \mathbb{Z}_p$.*

We now have all of the necessary tools to prove Theorem 1.

3. Proof of Theorem 1

Proof of Theorem 1. Let k be a positive integer, and $s_0(k)$, $\eta_0(k)$, and N_0 be as defined in Theorem 2. We may assume that $n = 3 \left\lceil \frac{s_0(k)}{2} \right\rceil$ by setting $n - 3 \left\lceil \frac{s_0(k)}{2} \right\rceil$ variables equal to arbitrary values in their specified intervals if $n > 3 \left\lceil \frac{s_0(k)}{2} \right\rceil$. We note that for $k = 2, 3$, we have

$$3 \left\lceil \frac{s_0(2)}{2} \right\rceil = 3 \left\lceil \frac{5}{2} \right\rceil = 9 \quad \text{and} \quad 3 \left\lceil \frac{s_0(3)}{2} \right\rceil = 3 \left\lceil \frac{8}{2} \right\rceil = 12.$$

Let $0 < \eta \leq \eta_0(k)$, p be prime, and c, a_i be integers such that $p \nmid a_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Set $B = \left\lfloor \left(\frac{3p}{n}\right)^{\frac{1}{k}} \right\rfloor$ and define $m = \left\lceil \frac{s_0(k)}{2} \right\rceil$.

If p is less than the implied constant in $1 \leq x_i \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$, then the x_i are any elements of the complete residue system modulo p . By Lemma 2, we have that

Equation (1) is solvable. Thus, we may assume that p is larger than any constant depending only on k as needed. In particular, we may assume that $p > \left\lceil \frac{s_0(k)}{2} \right\rceil$, so that $B \geq 1$.

We divide our variables into three sets, each with m elements. Define

$$A_1 := \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^m a_i x_i^k \in \mathbb{Z}_p : x_i \in \mathcal{A}, 1 \leq i \leq m \right\},$$

and define A_2 and A_3 similarly for the variables x_{m+1}, \dots, x_{2m} and x_{2m+1}, \dots, x_{3m} , respectively. We now apply Lemma 1 with n replaced by m , checking that $mB^k \leq p$ and $2m \geq s_0(k)$ by our definitions of B and m . Since $mB^k \leq p$, it follows from Lemma 1 that there exists a positive constant $c_0(k, \eta)$ with $|A_i| \geq c_0(k, \eta)p$ for $1 \leq i \leq 3$.

We set

$$L = \left\lceil \frac{k}{c_0(k, \eta)^3} \right\rceil$$

and take p to be sufficiently large so that $p > L$. Furthermore, we set $D = \{1^k, 2^k, 3^k, \dots, L^k\} \subseteq \mathbb{Z}_p$. Note that there are at least L/k distinct values mod p in the set D . Thus, $|A_1||A_2||A_3||D| > p^3$. Therefore, by Lemma 3, $A_1D + A_2 + A_3 = \mathbb{Z}_p$. It follows that for any integer c , there exists a solution to Equation (1) with $1 \leq x_i \leq LB \ll_k p^{\frac{1}{k}}$. \square

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